

Palladium-mediated cyclization of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones towards the synthesis of 7,8-furano-2-styrylchromones

C. Srinivas Rao, C. Jyotsna and Shakil S. Sait*

JNTUH, Dr. Reddy Laboratories, Hyderabad, India

E-mail : chemistrycsr@gmail.com

Manuscript received 17 February 2011, revised 13 December 2011, accepted 21 December 2011

Abstract : A rapid, efficient and practical synthesis of 7,8-furano-2-styrylchromones by oxidation of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones with dichlorobis(benzonitrile)palladium has been developed. This procedure is general and the products thus obtained have been characterized from their spectral data. DDQ oxidation of the same substrates, however, gave 7,8-pyrano-2-styrylchromone derivatives.

Keywords : 7,8-Furano-2-styrylchromones, 7,8-pyrano-2-styrylchromones, 7-hydroxy-3-methyl-2-styrylchromones, $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhCN})_2]$, DDQ.

Introduction

Chromones and isoflavones constitute an important class of oxygen heterocycles. Substituted as well as heterocyclic ring fused chromones and isoflavones have a wide range of pharmacological activities, chromones and isoflavones with medicinal use are khellin, a coronary vasodilator¹⁻⁵, chromones-2-carboxylate, a spasmolytic agent, disodium chromoglycate, an anti-energic drug, genstein having estrogen hormonal activity and 7-isopropoxyflavones used for treatment of postmenopausal and senile osteoporosis.

Results and discussion

A mixture of equimolar quantities of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-3-methyl-2-styrylchromone (**1a**) and dichlorobis(benzonitrile)palladium $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhCN})_2]$ taken in benzene on stirring for 30 min at room temperature gave 3,8-dimethyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4*H*-furano[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (**3a**) in good yield. The same reaction on **1b-d** also gave **3b-d** in good yield (Scheme 1, Table 1). DDQ oxidation of the substrates **1a-d**, however, gave the pyrone fused products **4a-d** (Scheme 2, Table 2).

The mechanistic pathway for the conversion of **1a** to **3a** involves the oxidative cyclisation of the sodium salts **2a-d** with $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhCN})_2]$ (Scheme 3). Formation of dimeric π -allylic complex is the key step in this reaction.

This π -allylic complex was possibly converted into insoluble monomer which gave rise to **3a-d** by successive elimination of NaCl, HCl and Pd.

Experimental

General : Melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Shimadzu 435 spectrometer, ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian Gemini 200 MHz spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi RDO-62 and MS-30 instrument.

General procedure for the synthesis of 8-methyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4*H*-furo[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-ones (3a-d**) :**

3, 8-Dimethyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4*H*-furanof[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (3a**) :**

A suspension of sodium salt of 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-3-methyl-2-styrylchromone (**1a**) (1.7 g, 5 mmol) in benzene (200 mL) containing $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhCN})_2$ (2.25 g) was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The suspension became clear and developed intense red colour during stirring. The clear solution was refluxed for 2 h when black metallic palladium separated out and the solution turned colorless. Palladium was filtered, and the filtrate concentrated to yield the crude product. The product was purified by column chromatography using silica gel (50 g, 200 mesh). Elution with benzene (200 ml) gave

Scheme 1

Table 1. [PdCl₂(PhCN)₂] oxidation of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones (1a-d)

Sl. no.	Starting material	Product	Time (h)	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.			3	120	74
2.			3	119	73
3.			3	124	70
4.			3	120	75

Note

Scheme 2

H-5); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 50.3 MHz) : δ 9.6 (CH₃-3), 14.1 (CH₃-8), 100.1 (C-9), 108.9 (C-4a, C-6), 117.5 (C-1, 9a), 117.8 (C-3), 117.9 (C- α), 121.0 (C-4'), 126.7 (C-2',6'), 127.5 (C-3',5'), 129.4 (C-5), 135.6 (C- β), 149.0 (C-8), 156.2 (C-6a,2), 158.0 (C-9b), 178.2 (C-4); MS : 316 (M⁺, 38%), 315 (100%), 301 (30%), 239 (100%), 174 (55%), 146.

Table 2. DDQ oxidation of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones (1a-d)

Sl. no.	Starting material	Product	Time (h)	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.			12	198	75
2.			12	237	73
3.			12	242	70
4.			12	204	74

benzonitrile and subsequent elution with chloroform gave 3,8-dimethyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-ethyl]-4*H*-furan[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (**3a**). It was recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals (1.4 g), m.p. 120 °C; UV (MeOH) : 214, 262, 346 nm; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1246, 1609, 2092, 3093; ^1H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) : δ 2.20 (s, CH₃-3), 2.55 (s, CH₃-8), 6.77 (s, H-9), 6.53 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.15 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- β), 7.38–7.50 (m, H-2',3',4',5',6'), 7.55 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α), 8.04 (d, *J* 10 Hz,

Similarly **3b-d** were obtained from **1b-d** in 70–75% yield.

3-Ethyl-8-methyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4*H*-furan[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (**3b**) :

It was recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 119 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1245, 1585, 1608, 2092, 3095; ^1H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) : δ 1.20 (t, CH₂-CH₃-3), 2.53 (s, CH₃-8), 2.79 (q, CH₂-CH₃-3), 6.80 (s, H-9), 6.95 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.15 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α),

Scheme 3

7.50 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-β), 7.35–7.45 (m, H-2',3',4',5',6'), 8.05 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-5).

*3-Phenyl-8-methyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H-furano[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (3c)* :

It was recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 124 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1245, 1585, 1612, 2928, 3070; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) : δ 2.55 (s, CH₃-8), 6.80 (s, H-9), 6.90 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-α), 6.94 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.10 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-α), 7.30–7.45 (10H, m, Ar-H), 7.50 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-β), 8.05 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-5).

*8-Methyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H-furano[2,3-*h*]chromen-4-one (3d)* :

It was recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 120 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1246, 1617, 3024, 3076; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) : δ 2.53 (s, CH₃-8),

6.25 (s, H-3), 6.70 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-α), 6.75 (s, H-9), 6.92 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6), 7.58 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-β), 7.37–7.50 (m, H-2',3',4',5',6'), 8.05 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-5).

*General procedure for the synthesis of 2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-*f*]chromen-4,8-diones (4a-d)* :

*3-Methyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-*f*]chromen-4,8-diones (4a)* :

A solution of 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-3-methyl-2-styrylchromone (**4a**) (3.18 g, 10 mmol) and 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) (6.81 g, 30 mmol) in benzene (100 mL) containing few drops of water was refluxed for 12 h on a steam bath. 2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-hydroquinone that separated was filtered off and benzene solution was washed with saturated sodium bisulphate solution (200 mL) followed by water. Benzene

layer was dried and concentrated under vacuum. The crude product thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (ACME, 200 mesh, 100 g). Elution with chloroform gave 3-methyl-2-[(*E*)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4*H*,8*H*-pyrano[2,3-*f*]chromen-4,8-dione (**5a**). It was recrystallized from chloroform gave as yellow crystals (2.6 g), mp. 198 °C; UV (MeOH) : 218, 267, 332 nm; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1287, 1369, 1410, 1626 (C=O), 1738 (C=O), 2919, 3055; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 2.25 (s, CH_3 -3), 6.58 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.17 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α), 7.28 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-9), 7.40 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H-13), 7.45 and 7.60 (m, H-3',4',5' and H-2',6'), 7.95 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5), 8.32 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-10); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 50.3 MHz) : δ 9.5 (CH_3 -3), 114.1 (C-10a), 117.9 (C_α), 159.4 (C-8), 176.8 (C-4); MS : 330 (M^+ , 13%), 329 (12%), 315 (44%), 301 (16%), 253 (12%), 115.

Similarly **4b-d** were obtained from **1b-d** in 70–75% yield.

3-Ethyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H,8H-pyrano [2,3-f]chromen-4,8-dione (4b) :

It is recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 237 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1286, 1573, 1624, 1730, 2916, 3052; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 1.20 (t, CH_2 - CH_3 -3), 2.80 (q, CH_2 - CH_3 -3), 6.62 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.16 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α), 7.32 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-9), 7.65 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- β), 7.45–7.60 (m, H-2',3',4',5',6'), 8.10 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5), 8.43 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-10).

3-Phenyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f]chromen-4,8-dione (4c) :

It is recrystallised from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 242 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1240, 1624, 1732, 2931, 3067; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 6.85 (d, *J*

10 Hz, H-6), 7.10 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α), 7.25 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-9), 7.30–7.45 (10H, m, Ar-H), 7.50 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- β), 8.10 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-5).

3-Methyl-2-[(E)-2-phenyl-1-ethenyl]-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f]chromen-4,8-dione (4c) :

It is recrystallized from chloroform as yellow crystals, m.p. 204 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 826, 1287, 1624, 1735, 2920, 3055; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 200 MHz) : δ 6.28 (s, H-3), 6.60 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-6), 7.14 (d, *J* 16 Hz, H- α), 7.30 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-9), 7.40 (m, H-3',4',5'), 7.60 (m, H- β -2',6'), 8.05 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5), 8.45 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-10).

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have developed an efficient and practical procedure for the synthesis of 7,8-furano-2-styrylchromones using $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhCN})_2]$.

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